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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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Yuldasheva N.A.,
Abdukhakimova M.B.,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
maftuna_bahromova@mail.ru

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE COMBINATION THERAPY OF HERPETIC STOMATITIS WITH THE ANTIVIRAL DRUG "PROTEFLAZID" AND THE IMMUNOMODULATOR "LIKOPID"

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of the treatment of 20 people suffering from herpes simplex with the help of the immunomodulatory medicine "Likopid" and the antiviral solution "Proteflazid". According to the obtained results, there were revealed an acceleration in the development of the manifestations of this disease and an increase in the period of remission with the help of above-mentioned medicines. The immune system was examined to confirmation of received data.

Keywords: herpetic stomatitis, therapy, proteflazid, licopid.

Юлдашева Н.А.,
Абдухакимова М.Б.,

Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт
maftuna_bahromova@mail.ru

ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КОМБИНИРОВАННОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ГЕРПЕТИЧЕСКОГО СТОМАТИТА ПРОТИВОВИРУСНЫМ ПРЕПАРАТОМ «ПРОТЕФЛАЗИД» И ИММУНОМОДУЛЯТОРОМ «ЛИКОПИД»

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье показаны данные лечения 20 человек, страдающих простым герпесом препаратом «Ликопид» и противовирусным препаратом «Протефлазид». По полученным результатам было выявлено ускорение купирования клинических проявлений данного заболевания и удлинение периода ремиссии при применении вышеуказанных препаратов. Была обследована система иммунитета для подтверждения полученных результатов.

Ключевые слова: герпетический стоматит, терапия, Протефлазид, Ликопид.

Yuldasheva N.A.,
Abduxakimova M.B.,
Toshkent Davlat Stomatologiya Instituti
maftuna_bahromova@mail.ru

"PROTEFLAZID" ANTIVIRUS PREPARATI VA "LIKOPID" IMMUNOMODULYATORI BILAN GERPETIK STOMATITNING KOMBINATSIYALANGAN TERAPIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTASIYA

Ushbu maqolada "Likopid" preparati va "Proteflazid" antiviral preparati bilan herpes simplex bilan og'rigan 20 kishining davolash ma'lumotlari ko'rsatilgan. Olingan natijalarga ko'ra, yuqoridagi dorilarni qo'llash bilan ushbu kasallikning klinik ko'rinishini engillashtirishning tezlashishi va remissiya davrining uzayishi aniqlandi. Natijalarni tasdiqlash uchun immunitet tizimi tekshirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: gerpetik stomatit, terapiya, Proteflazid, Likopid.

Introduction. Currently, chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis remains an urgent problem for doctors of all specialties, since among viral diseases, herpes is the most common viral infection in the human population, affecting all age categories of people and having a wide variety of clinical manifestations. Human infection with herpes simplex virus type 1 occurs in the first three years of life, and during puberty infection with herpes simplex virus type 2 occurs. The tendency of chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis to a long and often recurrent course is the most important feature of the infection under study.

The variability of the clinical symptoms of the herpes simplex virus depends on the state of the individual's immunity, which affects the course of the infectious process, increasing or decreasing the activity of the immunity components.

An immunodeficiency state was noted in people suffering from herpes types 1 and 2, which gives us the right to consider herpes virus infection as a disease of the immune system [2].

Activation of humoral immunity is accompanied by an exacerbation of herpes virus infection, and its indicators depend on the frequency of relapses of this disease. It is believed that humoral immunity occupies an important position in relieving the symptoms of relapse, but does not stop the process of relapse itself [3].

Immunoglobulins play an important role in the pathogenesis of the disease, since with each manifestation of the disease, a pronounced increase in antibody levels is observed. It is a fact that antibodies during relapses do not prevent the occurrence of an exacerbation, but also take part in the formation of pathological complexes of immunity or the manifestation of allergic reactions [4].

The expansion of the pathological focus and the addition of other systems to the inflammation process depends on an increase in the number of circulating immune complexes. The formation of endogenous intoxication of the body is observed, which is proved by a pronounced increase in the amount of malondialdehyde, which is considered a parameter of lipid peroxidation [5].

The course and development of the inflammation process depends on a complex of many factors, but the main one is the presence of damage, which is the leading initiator of the inflammatory process. In addition to the presence of damage, the trigger factor for inflammation is also the desire of the individual's body to eliminate the agent of damage and repair, namely, to restore homeostasis.

It should also be noted that the phlogogenic factor is a pathological stimulus, which in its duration and strength dominates the adaptive capabilities of the tissue, which causes the process of inflammation [6].

The use of antiviral drugs did not completely solve this problem. In addition, the number of resistant forms to antiviral agents is increasing. In this regard, to optimize the treatment of herpes stomatitis, we used a comprehensive approach to treatment with the antiviral drug Proteflazid, which is a phytopreparation capable of suppressing virus-specific thymidine kinase and DNA polymerase enzymes in cells infected with herpes simplex viruses (Herpes simplex types 1 and 2), which in turn contributes to a decrease or complete blocking of viral replication, as well as the immunomodulatory drug "Likopid", the active substance of which is glucosaminylmuramyl dipeptide (GMDP), which is a synthetic analogue of the structural fragment of the shell (peptidoglycan) of bacterial cells and has an activating effect of innate and acquired immunity, which enhances the body's defense against viral,

bacterial and fungal infections and has an adjuvant effect in the development of immunological reactions.

Purpose of the study. The main goal of this work is to determine the effectiveness and safety of the combination therapy of herpes infection with Proteflazid and Likopid.

Materials and methods. 20 people aged 18 to 70 years old with a history of a disease associated with herpetic stomatitis were examined. The frequency of recurrence of this disease in the surveyed ranged from 2 to 4 times a year.

The inclusion criteria for the study were:

- age of patients from 18 to 70 years;
- Diagnosis of "chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis";
- Availability of consent of the patient to conduct examination and therapy.

Based on clinical data, namely the presence of a lesion of the oral mucosa and the red border of the lips, a diagnosis was made. Before the start of the study, each patient was noted to have itching, pain in the area of rashes, burning, edema and hyperemia, and regional lymphadenitis. The number of rashes was 2 or more.

The patients were divided into 2 groups of 10 people. The first group was treated with acyclovir 1 tablet 5 times a day before bedtime for 5 days. For local treatment in this group, "Calendula tincture" was used, by rinsing the affected areas with this drug 5 times a day for 5 days. Patients of the 2nd group were prescribed treatment with proteflazid 10 drops 3 times a day for 5 days and licopid 1 tablet on an empty stomach for 5 days, and calendula tincture was used locally in the form of mouth rinses 4-5 times a day, 5 days. In the presence of relapses of the disease, a second course of treatment was prescribed for all patients. The survey was conducted twice: before the start of the study and on the 14th day of the study. The study material was saliva. Statistical processing of the results of the study was carried out.

Research results. Before the start of the study, each patient was noted to have itching, pain in the area of rashes, burning, edema and hyperemia, and regional lymphadenitis. The number of rashes was 2 or more.

The presence of HSV-1 and HSV-2 types was confirmed in all patients by the results of laboratory tests. Diagnosis was carried out by polymerase chain reaction, which gave us the opportunity to determine the presence of HSV-1 and HSV-2 types in saliva. HSV-1 type was detected in 8 women (73.6%) and 4 men (28.5%), HSV-2 type was detected in 6 women (62.8%) and 5 men (35.7%), which corresponds to the data given by other authors [7, 8, 9, 10, 11].

Based on the data obtained, it can be understood that HSV-1 type is more common in patients (54.5%), while HSV-2 occurs in half of the patients who participated in the study (51.5%). It was also proved a direct relationship between the severity of the course of the disease and the amount of virus DNA isolated in 1 ml of saliva. The highest amount of HSV-1 and type 2 virus DNA was found in patients with severe disease.

14 days after the start of therapy in group 1, the pain syndrome subsided in 75%, the presence of swelling and hyperemia in the area of the rash was found in 10%. In the 2nd group, the pain syndrome stopped in 95% of the examined patients, swelling and hyperemia of the affected area remained only in 5% of the patients.

Conclusion. It was proved that the combined treatment with the antiviral drug "Proteflazid" and the immunomodulator "Likopid" was effective in the treatment of chronic recurrent herpetic stomatitis, which allows to achieve the most rapid relief of clinical manifestations and stable, long-term remission of the disease.

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